

1 Appendix A: Mathematical Derivation of DECAL

2 We consider $\mathbf{x} \in Cl_{p,q,r}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ that we represent using $p + q + r$
3 orthogonal vectors as $\mathbf{x} = x_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p x_i e_i + \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} x_j e_j +$
4 $\sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} x_k e_k$, where $x_{(\cdot)} \in \mathbb{R}^{\lfloor \frac{d}{1+p+q+r} \rfloor}$. The norm of $\mathbf{x}$, denoted $\|\mathbf{x}\|$,
5 is defined using the quadratic form Q that govern $Cl_{p,q,r}$. Since Q is degenerate,
6 the norm only operates on non-degenerate vectors [?], i.e.

$$\|\mathbf{x}\|^2 = Q(\mathbf{x}) = x_0^2 + \sum_{i=1}^p x_i^2 e_i^2 - \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} x_j^2 e_j^2 = \sum_{i=0}^{p+q} x_i^2. \quad (1)$$

8 If we take also $\mathbf{y} \in Cl_{p,q,r}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ such that

$$\mathbf{y} = y_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p y_i e_i + \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} y_j e_j + \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} y_k e_k, \quad (2)$$

9 the inner product $\mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{y}$ between $\mathbf{x}$ and $\mathbf{y}$ is given by

$$x_0 \cdot y_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p x_i \cdot y_i + \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} x_j \cdot y_j + \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} x_k \cdot y_k.$$

10 The Clifford product $\mathbf{x} \circ \mathbf{y}$ between vectors $\mathbf{x}$ and $\mathbf{y}$ involves element-
11 wise multiplication of their components across different basis elements (see Appendix A
12 for mathematical details).

13 Let be $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in Cl_{p,q,r}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ such that

$$\mathbf{x} = x_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p x_i e_i + \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} x_j e_j + \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} x_k e_k \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{y} = y_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p y_i e_i + \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} y_j e_j + \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} y_k e_k, \quad (4)$$

14 with $x_{(\cdot)}, y_{(\cdot)} \in \mathbb{R}^m$.

15 We start by reminding that:

$$\text{DECAL}(\langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z} \rangle) = (\mathbf{x} \circ \mathbf{y}) \cdot \mathbf{z}. \quad (5)$$

16 The Clifford multiplication $\mathbf{x} \circ \mathbf{y}$ between $\mathbf{x}$ and $\mathbf{y}$, which consists
17 of taking element wise multiplication between components of $\mathbf{x}$ and
18 $\mathbf{y}$, can be expanded as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x} \circ \mathbf{y} &= x_0 y_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p x_0 y_i e_i + \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} x_0 y_j e_j + \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} x_0 y_k e_k + \\ &\sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=1}^p x_i y_j e_i e_j + \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} x_i y_j e_i e_j + \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} x_i y_k e_i e_k + \\ &\sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} x_i y_k e_i e_k + \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} \sum_{i=1}^p x_j y_i e_j e_i + \sum_{i=p+1}^{p+q} \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} x_j y_i e_j e_i + \\ &\sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} x_j y_k e_j e_k + \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} x_j y_k e_j e_k + \\ &\sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} x_j y_k e_j e_k + \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} x_j y_k e_j e_k + \\ &\sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} x_j y_k e_j e_k + \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} x_j y_k e_j e_k + \\ &\sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} x_j y_k e_j e_k + \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} x_j y_k e_j e_k. \end{aligned}$$

Using the properties of the orthogonal base vectors of $Cl_{p,q,r}(\mathbb{R})$,
i.e.,

$$\begin{cases} e_i^2 = 1, \forall i \in \{1, \dots, p\} \\ e_j^2 = -1, \forall j \in \{p+1, \dots, p+q\} \\ e_k^2 = 0, \forall k \in \{p+q+1, \dots, p+q+r\} \\ e_\ell e_n = -e_n e_\ell, \forall n \neq \ell, \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

the product $\mathbf{x} \circ \mathbf{y}$ reduces to:

$$\mathbf{x} \circ \mathbf{y} = \sigma_0 + \sigma_p + \sigma_q + \sigma_r + \sigma_{p,p} + \sigma_{q,q} + \sigma_{r,r} + \sigma_{p,q} + \sigma_{p,r} + \sigma_{q,r},$$

where

$$\sigma_0 = x_0 y_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p x_i y_i - \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} x_j y_j \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_p = \sum_{i=1}^p (x_0 y_i + x_i y_0) e_i \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_q = \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} (x_0 y_j + x_j y_0) e_j \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma_r = \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} (x_0 y_k + x_k y_0) e_k \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma_{p,p} = \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \sum_{i'=i+1}^p (x_i y_{i'} - x_{i'} y_i) e_i e_{i'} \quad (11)$$

$$\sigma_{q,q} = \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q-1} \sum_{j'=j+1}^{p+q} (x_j y_{j'} - x_{j'} y_j) e_j e_{j'} \quad (12)$$

$$\sigma_{r,r} = \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r-1} \sum_{k'=k+1}^p (x_k y_{k'} - x_{k'} y_k) e_k e_{k'} \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma_{p,r} = \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} (x_i y_k - x_k y_i) e_i e_k \quad (14)$$

$$\sigma_{q,r} = \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} (x_j y_k - x_k y_j) e_j e_k. \quad (15)$$

To perform the scalar product in Equation (5), we represent $\mathbf{z}$ as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z} &= z_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p z_i e_i + \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} z_j e_j + \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} z_k e_k + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \\ &\sum_{i'=i+1}^p e_i e_{i'} + \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q-1} \sum_{j'=j+1}^{p+q} e_j e_{j'} + \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r-1} \sum_{k'=k+1}^p \\ &e_k e_{k'} + \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} e_i e_j + \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} e_i e_k + \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} \\ &\sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} e_j e_k, \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $z_{(\cdot)} \in \mathbb{R}^m$. Thus, the scoring function of DECAL is given

25 by:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{DECAL}(\langle x, Y, z \rangle) &= x_0 y_0 z_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p x_i y_i z_0 - \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} x_j y_j z_0 + \\
&\sum_{i=1}^p (x_0 y_i z_i + x_i y_0 z_i) + \sigma_{p,p}^* + \sigma_{q,q}^* + \\
&\sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} (x_0 y_j z_j + x_j y_0 z_j) + \sigma_{r,r}^* + \sigma_{p,q}^* \\
&+ \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} (x_0 y_k z_k + x_k y_0 z_k) + \sigma_{p,r}^* \\
&+ \sigma_{q,r}^*
\end{aligned}$$

26 where

$$\sigma_{p,p}^* = \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \sum_{i'=i+1}^p (x_i y_{i'} - x_{i'} y_i) \quad (17)$$

$$\sigma_{q,q}^* = \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q-1} \sum_{j'=j+1}^{p+q} (x_j y_{j'} - x_{j'} y_j) \quad (18)$$

$$\sigma_{r,r}^* = \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r-1} \sum_{k'=k+1}^p (x_k y_{k'} - x_{k'} y_k) \quad (19)$$

$$\sigma_{p,q}^* = \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} (x_i y_j - x_j y_i) \quad (20)$$

$$\sigma_{p,r}^* = \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{k=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} (x_i y_k - x_k y_i) \quad (21)$$

$$\sigma_{q,r}^* = \sum_{j=p+1}^{p+q} \sum_{j'=p+q+1}^{p+q+r} (x_j y_{j'} - x_{j'} y_j). \quad (22)$$

27 2 Appendix B: Link Prediction Results on Train, Validation and Test datasets

28
29 Here we show the results of the evaluation of the models during the
30 test, train and validation time. The results on the WN18RR dataset
31 can be found in Table 2, for the UMLS, KINSHIP and NELL-995-
32 h100 in Table 3 and for NELL-995-h75, NELL-995-h50 and FB15k-
33 237 in Table ???. In table 1, We have the choosed Clifford space for
34 the embeddings of each DECAL searches algorithm and KECI as well
35 as the computational time of every search.

36 3 Appendix C: Visualization of GSDC and LES triples scores

37 **Figure 1:** A visualisation of the MRR function for the UMLS dataset
with triples $(p, q, r) \in [0, 4]^3$.

38 In Table 4, we present a 3D plot illustrating the MRR of triples
39 with respect to feasible triples—those satisfying the condition 1 +

40 $p + q + r$ divides d , where $d = 16$. This analysis is conducted for
41 each dataset across the training, testing, and validation data.

42 The scatter plot reveals three distinct levels in the space. The
43 first level comprises a minority of points, representing low values
44 of (p, q, r) . The second level corresponds to mid-range values, while
45 the third level encompasses the highest values of (p, q, r) . Notably,
46 we observe a uniform distribution of triples across all levels and
47 datasets, indicating that the location of optimal triples on the test set
48 remain the same on both the training and validation sets.

49 Upon closer inspection of the Table, we find that on the KINSHIP
50 dataset, the best triples predominantly belong to the first level, where
51 $(p, q, r) \leq 4$. Conversely, for the remaining datasets, optimal triples
52 are distributed across both the first and second levels, with $(p, q, r) \leq$
53 8. An exception to this pattern is observed in the NELL-995-h100
54 dataset, where optimal triples require examination across the entire
55 domain.

56 The MRR function is defined as:

$$\hat{\text{MRR}} : \mathbb{N}^3 \longrightarrow \mathbb{R} : (p, q, r) \longmapsto \text{MRR}(p, q, r) \quad (23)$$

57 Figure 1 shows a visualization of the MRR function on the UMLS
58 dataset. Our Greedy search is then define as

$$\text{DECAL} + \text{GS} = \underset{p, q, r \in [0, 4]}{\text{argmax}} \hat{\text{MRR}}(p, q, r) \quad (24)$$

59 Although the function is continuous (by considering as a function
60 of $\mathbb{R}$), it contains numerous local maxima, posing challenges in
61 finding the global maximum. Consequently, the results of DECAL
62 + GS are heavily influenced by the choice of initial starting points.
63 Throughout the experiments, we opted to use the triple $(1, 1, 1)$ as
64 the starting point across all datasets.

Table 1: Space discovery and time efficiency of DECAL’s searches algorithm and KECI

Datasets	GSDC		LES		GS		KECI	
	Space	time(hr)	Space	time(hr)	Space	time(hr)	Space	time(hr)
UMLS	$Cl_{6,0,1}(\mathbb{R}^2)$	0.11	$Cl_{0,0,4}(\mathbb{R}^3)$	0.07	$Cl_{3,2,1}(\mathbb{R}^2)$	0.03	$Cl_{6,1}(\mathbb{R}^2)$	0.06
KINSHIP	$Cl_{0,1,0}(\mathbb{R}^8)$	0.12	$Cl_{0,1,0}(\mathbb{R}^8)$	0.08	$Cl_{0,1,0}(\mathbb{R}^8)$	0.03	$Cl_{0,1}(\mathbb{R}^8)$	0.07
NELL-995-h100	$Cl_{10,4,1}(\mathbb{R})$	3.83	$Cl_{1,2,0}(\mathbb{R}^4)$	2.57	$Cl_{1,2,0}(\mathbb{R}^4)$	0.87	$Cl_{2,13}(\mathbb{R})$	2.17
NELL-995-h75	$Cl_{4,2,9}(\mathbb{R})$	5.43	$Cl_{4,2,1}(\mathbb{R}^2)$	3.65	$Cl_{1,3,2}(\mathbb{R}^2)$	1.49	$Cl_{4,3}(\mathbb{R}^2)$	3.08
NELL-995-h50	$Cl_{13,2,0}(\mathbb{R})$	7.89	$Cl_{0,4,4}(\mathbb{R})$	5.30	$Cl_{2,0,2}(\mathbb{R}^3)$	1.95	$Cl_{13,2}(\mathbb{R})$	4.48
FB15k-237	$Cl_{5,0,2}(\mathbb{R}^2)$	13.05	$Cl_{4,1,2}(\mathbb{R}^2)$	8.77	$Cl_{3,3,1}(\mathbb{R}^2)$	4.49	$Cl_{5,2}(\mathbb{R}^2)$	7.41
WN18-RR	$Cl_{0,1,6}(\mathbb{R}^2)$	15.86	$Cl_{0,0,3}(\mathbb{R}^4)$	10.66	$Cl_{0,2,1}(\mathbb{R}^4)$	2.81	$Cl_{0,1}(\mathbb{R}^8)$	9.01
Relative Time ¹	-	100%	-	67.6%	-	≈ 24.3%	-	56.7%

Table 2: Link prediction results on UMLS, KINSHIP, and NELL-995-h100. Bold and underlined results indicate the best and second-best results respectively. The first, second and third row of each algorithm stand for the performance of said algorithm at training, validation, and test time, respectively.

Models	UMLS				KINSHIP				NELL-995-h100			
	MRR	H@1	H@3	H@10	MRR	H@1	H@3	H@10	MRR	H@1	H@3	H@10
DistMult	0.883	0.819	0.937	0.986	0.582	0.429	0.665	0.908	0.654	0.567	0.706	0.819
	0.760	0.653	0.841	0.948	0.520	0.357	0.602	0.880	0.202	0.134	0.222	0.345
	0.756	0.647	0.834	0.952	0.514	0.346	0.606	0.878	0.185	0.120	0.205	0.320
ComplEx	0.939	0.889	<u>0.989</u>	<u>0.997</u>	0.786	<u>0.680</u>	0.869	<u>0.973</u>	0.619	0.530	0.672	0.785
	0.834	0.729	0.934	0.968	<u>0.737</u>	<u>0.612</u>	0.831	<u>0.962</u>	0.175	0.114	0.192	0.297
	0.835	0.728	0.939	0.976	<u>0.725</u>	<u>0.594</u>	<u>0.821</u>	<u>0.963</u>	0.168	0.109	0.187	0.285
QMult	0.944	0.901	0.986	0.996	0.688	0.562	0.772	0.930	0.384	0.293	0.428	0.558
	0.855	0.776	0.924	0.970	0.639	0.502	<u>0.719</u>	0.917	0.131	0.084	0.142	0.227
	0.859	0.773	0.936	0.980	0.624	0.481	0.715	0.911	0.125	0.079	0.135	0.214
OMult	0.912	0.866	0.947	0.985	0.525	0.406	0.577	0.767	0.346	0.271	0.369	0.498
	0.844	0.784	0.883	0.951	0.493	0.371	0.539	0.738	0.145	0.095	0.159	0.240
	0.827	0.756	0.874	0.954	0.488	0.365	0.536	0.747	0.137	0.088	0.151	0.237
KECI	0.949	0.908	<u>0.988</u>	0.997	0.788	0.680	0.875	0.974	0.656	0.553	0.726	0.845
	0.880	0.810	0.939	0.977	0.739	0.619	0.831	0.963	0.262	0.181	0.300	0.423
	0.875	<u>0.798</u>	0.944	0.983	0.743	0.621	0.830	0.964	0.252	0.174	0.288	0.408
DECAL + LES	<u>0.947</u>	<u>0.905</u>	0.988	<u>0.997</u>	0.788	0.680	0.875	0.974	0.715	0.630	0.770	0.870
	0.886	0.815	0.950	0.985	0.739	0.619	0.831	0.963	<u>0.261</u>	<u>0.187</u>	<u>0.289</u>	<u>0.411</u>
	0.883	0.799	0.962	0.991	0.743	0.621	0.830	0.964	<u>0.256</u>	<u>0.184</u>	<u>0.280</u>	<u>0.399</u>
DECAL + GSDC	0.941	0.895	0.985	0.996	0.788	0.680	0.875	0.974	<u>0.688</u>	<u>0.596</u>	0.749	0.856
	<u>0.885</u>	<u>0.814</u>	<u>0.949</u>	0.979	0.739	0.619	0.831	0.963	0.278	0.201	0.311	0.433
	0.878	0.799	0.947	<u>0.989</u>	0.743	0.621	0.830	0.964	0.270	0.196	0.299	0.417
DECAL + GS	0.944	0.900	0.988	<u>0.997</u>	0.788	0.680	0.875	0.974	0.715	0.630	0.770	0.870
	0.873	0.795	0.940	<u>0.983</u>	0.739	0.619	0.831	0.963	<u>0.261</u>	<u>0.187</u>	<u>0.289</u>	<u>0.411</u>
	<u>0.879</u>	0.797	<u>0.951</u>	0.987	0.743	0.621	0.830	0.964	<u>0.256</u>	<u>0.184</u>	<u>0.280</u>	<u>0.399</u>
DECAL + VSP	0.943	0.893	0.993	0.998	0.713	0.589	0.801	0.950	0.687	0.592	<u>0.751</u>	<u>0.861</u>
	0.841	0.745	0.924	0.965	0.673	0.538	0.760	0.934	0.243	0.174	0.270	0.383
	0.843	0.732	0.944	0.986	0.674	0.540	0.766	0.942	0.235	0.167	0.259	0.374

Table 3: Link prediction results on NELL-995-h75, NELL-995-h50 and FB15k-237. Bold and underlined results indicate the best and second-best results respectively. The first, second and third row of each algorithm stand for the performance of said algorithm at training, validation, and test time, respectively.

Models	NELL-995-h75				NELL-995-h50				FB15k-237			
	MRR	H@1	H@3	H@10	MRR	H@1	H@3	H@10	MRR	H@1	H@3	H@10
DistMult	0.581	0.502	0.619	0.734	0.468	0.386	0.507	0.622	0.179	0.109	0.197	0.321
	0.167	0.107	0.185	0.285	0.146	0.095	0.164	0.248	0.147	0.091	0.159	0.260
	0.163	0.104	0.179	0.282	0.151	0.097	0.168	0.256	0.147	0.093	0.158	0.260
ComplEx	0.452	0.368	0.494	0.609	0.482	0.393	0.526	0.651	0.164	0.100	0.181	0.296
	0.136	0.082	0.152	0.248	0.159	0.105	0.177	0.268	0.137	0.086	0.146	0.240
	0.139	0.085	0.156	0.245	0.163	0.107	0.183	0.275	0.137	0.087	0.147	0.239
QMult	0.506	0.413	0.555	0.679	0.219	0.159	0.239	0.334	0.146	0.090	0.157	0.257
	0.161	0.109	0.176	0.265	0.098	0.0578	0.110	0.179	0.122	0.078	0.129	0.209
	0.158	0.106	0.171	0.261	0.101	0.0596	0.114	0.185	0.122	0.077	0.128	0.208
OMult	0.363	0.280	0.395	0.529	0.346	0.273	0.374	0.492	0.103	0.067	0.107	0.171
	0.128	0.078	0.143	0.227	0.120	0.075	0.134	0.205	0.085	0.135	0.087	0.059
	0.129	0.082	0.142	0.223	0.119	0.076	0.131	0.210	0.086	0.059	0.089	0.138
KECI	<u>0.695</u>	<u>0.608</u>	<u>0.750</u>	<u>0.853</u>	<u>0.573</u>	<u>0.468</u>	<u>0.638</u>	<u>0.765</u>	<u>0.285</u>	<u>0.193</u>	<u>0.318</u>	<u>0.468</u>
	0.242	0.171	0.271	0.379	0.253	0.179	0.288	0.394	<u>0.238</u>	0.166	<u>0.259</u>	<u>0.380</u>
	0.237	0.172	0.260	0.365	0.250	0.177	0.281	0.392	<u>0.235</u>	0.164	0.255	<u>0.376</u>
DECAL + LES	0.678	0.586	0.737	0.846	0.345	0.254	0.374	0.535	0.278	0.186	0.311	0.459
	<u>0.249</u>	<u>0.177</u>	<u>0.276</u>	<u>0.393</u>	<u>0.232</u>	0.164	<u>0.255</u>	<u>0.368</u>	0.237	<u>0.167</u>	0.258	0.377
	<u>0.245</u>	<u>0.177</u>	<u>0.274</u>	0.374	<u>0.232</u>	<u>0.166</u>	<u>0.253</u>	<u>0.368</u>	0.235	0.164	<u>0.258</u>	0.375
DECAL + GSDC	0.746	0.663	0.804	0.890	<u>0.573</u>	0.468	<u>0.638</u>	<u>0.765</u>	0.295	0.202	0.328	0.480
	0.255	0.182	0.283	0.401	0.253	0.179	0.288	0.394	0.243	0.172	0.265	0.382
	0.251	0.178	0.281	0.396	0.250	0.177	0.281	0.392	0.241	0.171	0.263	0.380
DECAL + GS	0.661	0.573	0.715	0.825	0.376	0.282	0.413	0.564	0.250	0.166	0.277	0.418
	0.244	0.173	0.269	0.388	0.161	0.109	0.174	0.266	0.220	0.152	0.242	0.353
	0.230	0.170	0.268	<u>0.376</u>	0.163	0.106	0.183	0.273	0.217	0.150	0.236	0.349
DECAL+VSP	0.442	0.344	0.485	0.640	0.613	0.519	0.666	0.789	0.145	0.091	0.154	0.252
	0.207	0.138	0.233	0.348	0.200	0.138	0.220	0.326	0.143	0.089	0.155	0.253
	0.202	0.136	0.225	0.335	0.203	0.138	0.229	0.333	0.144	0.091	0.156	0.251

Table 4: 3-D visualization of feasible triples (p,q,r) with their corresponding MRR of the GSDC search at train, test and validation time for every dataset.

